

TÂNĂRUL CERCETĂTOR

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INTER-INSTITUTIONAL COLLABORATION IN THE CONTEXT OF RURAL CRIME PREVENTION

At the present stage, it is becoming increasingly apparent that, in the activity of crime prevention, an exhaustive result is not possible with the police forces alone. Regardless of the specificity of the community, urban or rural, it is necessary to involve public authorities, educational institutions, public associations, religious denominations, etc. The development of customised strategies on the security and prevention of rural crime, following the example of other states, by creating partnerships primarily with citizens and inter-institutional collaboration, leads to the identification and resolution of problems on a given territory and responds to the needs and requirements of the community. This not only enhances the effectiveness of public security interventions, but also contributes to strengthening social cohesion and promoting a safe and prosperous environment for all inhabitants of rural communities.

Only through inter-institutional collaboration it is possible to achieve an optimal result in the prevention of rural crime.

Keywords: crime, rural, police, collaboration, prevention, study.

COLABORAREA INTER-INSTITUȚIONALĂ ÎN CONTEXTUL PREVENIRII CRIMINALITĂȚII DIN MEDIUL RURAL

La etapa actuală, tot mai evident devine faptul că, în activitatea de prevenire a criminalității, doar cu forțele polițienești nu este posibil de atins un rezultat exhaustiv. Indiferent de specificul comunității, urbane sau rurale, în activitatea de prevenire este necesară implicarea autorităților publice, instituțiilor de învățământ, asociațiilor obștești, cultelor religioase etc. Dezvoltarea strategiilor particularizate cu privire la securitatea și prevenirea criminalității rurale, după exemplul altor state, prin crearea de parteneriate în primul rând cu cetățenii și colaborarea interinstituțională, duce la identificarea și soluționarea problemelor pe un anumit teritoriu și răspunde la nevoile și cerințele comunității. Acest fapt nu numai că amplifică eficacitatea intervențiilor în domeniul securității publice, dar contribuie și la consolidarea coeziunii sociale și la promovarea unui mediu sigur și prosper pentru toți locuitorii comunităților rurale.

Doar printr-o colaborare interinstituțională este posibilă atingerea unui rezultat optim în activitatea de prevenire a criminalității din mediul rural.

Cuvinte-cheie: criminalitate, mediu rural, poliție, colaborare, prevenire, studiu.

1. INTRODUCTION.

By virtue of the implementation of various crime prevention strategies, the role of the local community in preventing and combating crime is crucial. Certain factors, such as the collaboration of educational institutions [18] with local authorities, exert a direct influence on antisocial behaviour and crime in general. It is clear that the community manifests such influence indirectly, through culture and norms that can either discourage or encourage the criminal behaviour of the person belonging to that community.

Remarkable is the fact that, without an interaction between the subjects of prevention, achieving the proposed goal is much more difficult, and even sometimes impossible, because ideally, only the removal of all factors that contribute to the occurrence of crime can lead to the desired result. For the rural community, the interaction between the subjects of crime prevention is much more productive taking into account the specifics of the rural environment, and the qualitative cooperation between all the subjects involved will lead to the achievement of the desired objective.

2. METHODOLOGY.

The following scientific research methods were used in the study: systemic analysis, logical analysis and comparative analysis. The materials used are: international criminological literature, national normative framework and other studies.

3. RESULTS ACHIEVED AND DISCUSSIONS.

An important role in the prevention of crime in rural areas lies on the process of collaboration between different state authorities and the community, which are carried out through crime prevention strategies and programmes, which are necessary to implement at

all levels in rural communities.

Looking at international practice, we find that, within the various community police services, customised strategies have been developed regarding the security and prevention of rural crime. For example, in the United Kingdom, the Rural Security Strategy [12], which involves the commitment of rural communities in solving local crime issues, has been approved. At the heart of this initiative is the creation of rural security groups, which are responsible for collecting data on local crime issues and identifying the most effective ways to prevent crime to address these problems.

A research conducted in Australia revealed that the challenges faced by law enforcement officers in rural communities were attributed to the rationalisation of certain crimes by residents and their reluctance to cooperate with law enforcement. The most efficient police officers in this rural context resorted to the traditional model of community police, i.e. the officers integrated into the community and exercised their discernment regarding the Community rules of conduct [14].

While some preventive approaches may be easier to describe than others, social crime prevention strategies generally assume that the origin of crime is, in a certain way, linked to the structure of society, which makes these strategies geared towards crime prevention in a social context.

For example, the "Neighbourhood Watch" programme, implemented in England in the 1980s, is identified as: "a network of civic community members who monitors what is happening in their neighbourhood and reports suspicious actions to the police. In simple terms, the citizen becomes the "eyes and ears" of the police in the rural community, looking for the usual and unusual to protect his own home and that of his neighbour, thus reducing opportunities for criminal activity.

The concept of neighbourhood monitoring, originally implemented in England, over time has been adjusted and modified in a variety of other contexts, taking deep roots and, at this stage, constitutes a model of inter-institutional cooperation between state authorities, being implemented in several countries around the world [3, 13, 15].

The neighbourhood surveillance program also gained a rather broad spread in the United States, and the authors who studied the given program found that in all eligible combined studies, this program was associated with a reduction in crime [6 p. 28].

The Republic of Moldova has also taken over the idea of institutional collaboration outlined above within the concept of community police activity, which involves targeting police services to citizens' needs, responsiveness to community problems and effective communication between police and community. Similarly, with the support of the Eco-Rezeni civil society, in 2015 the "Neighbourhood Supervision" program was established, which had the slogan "The best cop is your neighbor". In other words, the inhabitants of a community take care of the security of the neighbor, getting involved and informing the police when they notice something dubious in the locality where they live.

Therefore, the Government of the Republic of Moldova approved the Concept of Community Police Activity and the Action Plan for 2018-2020 on its implementation [7]. The document does not require the creation of a new police service or a separate structure, but rather a model of police activity in common with society, in order to solve the problems of crime and public security [10].

Community police is defined as "a policy and strategy geared towards a more efficient and effective control of crime, better quality of life, better police services and the legitimacy of the police, through pro-active reliance on community resources, which seeks to change the conditions that cause crime. This entails the need for a higher level of police accountability, a higher share of public participation in decision-making and a higher level of concern for civil rights and freedoms" [7].

First, community policing is a partnership, with citizens, for identifying and solving problems in a given territory, responding to the needs and demands of the community. Employees of the police sector cannot solve any problem independently, in particular those concerning public security or security. In this context, the involvement of the population can determine, as an effect, the identification and development of solutions to existing problems in the community. Collaborating and coordinating preventive activities with other partners, analysing problems and finding solutions to these problems is in fact the essence of community policing [4].

Unlike other countries, there are no well-founded mechanisms or any in-depth studies in the Republic of Moldova that would identify the operational framework for interaction between state authorities and local public authorities in order to prevent rural crime.

The information placed by some local public authorities regarding the working session on the topic "Cooperation between police and local authorities [11]" carried out between representatives of the local public authority and the management of the police inspectorate, remains without purpose, since no public information is subsequently placed on what the practical results of these meetings are. However, they are formal in nature or are limited only to some reports or briefings for internal use regarding the working sessions.

Although the problem of crime is found in all the programs of activity of the Government of the Republic of Moldova, these phenomena have a low degree of priority in the activity of law enforcement, due to the lack of well-defined legal and institutional instruments, which lead to the perpetuation of the culture of violence in society.

This gap can be removed by carrying out theoretical and well-reasoned studies, which would be perceived by the central public authorities in order to organise practical measures, first with the organisation of seminars or round tables aimed at training in priority the police officers working in rural communities, including small towns, with informing them

about the peculiarities of the activity within a rural community.

In rural areas, police employees are generally perceived as members of the local community, which gives them the opportunity to adopt different strategies from their urban peers. Thanks to a stronger social density in rural communities, police officers and citizens have a personal mutual acquaintance. As a result, rural policemen often resort to existing moral consensus. In contrast, in urban areas characterised by weaker moral consensus and often with a discrepancy between police and citizens, the police use more often stricter forms of law enforcement.

Analysing the incidence of crime in urban and rural areas, in the specific context of each region, can help public authorities to make more pertinent decisions that gives the possibility to implement effective crime prevention strategies.

Unquestionably, the Government plays an important role in monitoring the institutional collaboration and the implementation of the crime prevention policy and the management of programs, which can be quite intriguing. As an example, in the United Kingdom, the Crime Reduction Programme in the 1990s was coordinated through a series of inter-institutional committees linked to a cabinet subcommittee on the one hand and regional and local committees on the other, such as Local Partnerships for Crime Reduction and Disorders [9].

In Australia, crime prevention activity in the States of New South Wales and Western Australia is coordinated through similar Cabinet-level committees linked to a central, regional and local advisory board and inter-institutional forums [1 pp. 4-7, 2 p. 26, 9] as was previously the case in Victoria [5]. Similar structures can be identified in New Zealand [16] where the United Nations Guidelines on Crime Prevention are recommended in principle [20].

We believe that this collaborative approach is not only characteristic in the field of crime prevention. Moreover, it is an example of a more general change in public administration, from a model of governance through

command and control to one of government through the collaboration of several stakeholders, which has the mission to provide integrated solutions to social problems in different sectors and levels of government. In Australia, this type of approach is commonly described as “government for all” or “in the whole community”. In some regions of the United States, it is known as “network government”, while in the United Kingdom the approach is known as “united governance” [17].

In the process of examining the structure and content of the current crime prevention programs in the Republic of Moldova, through a comparative analysis with similar initiatives of other governments, it is noted that the approach adopted by the Republic of Moldova generally focuses on crime prevention and assistance of victims of crime, without providing specific directions, as is the case with the states whose programmes have been discussed. This suggests the need for the Government of the Republic of Moldova to develop programmes that pay greater attention to the prevention of rural crime.

The subjects of this programme should not only be reduced to the police and the rural community, but should also include other entities within public authorities working together in their working process. In this context, it would be beneficial to create a mechanism to coordinate collaboration within local multidisciplinary teams to address issues such as domestic violence, human traffic, violence against children and others.

Currently, there are multiple multidisciplinary teams and community safety councils, which are usually made up of social workers, police officers, pedagogues, family doctors, mayors, lawyers and other professionals, who have as one of the activity objectives crime prevention at local level. It is therefore essential to strengthen and coordinate these teams in order to optimise approaches to crime prevention.

As I have mentioned, rural crime contains a specificity of its own in terms of the subject matter of the criminal attack and the manner in which it is committed. However, in addition to these categories of crimes, there are also crimes

that occur in the urban environment, such as crimes against family and minors, thefts from the owner's property, hooliganisms, etc., the commission of which in rural localities is not known to the competent authorities, or to pay due attention to their investigation. Sometimes about the presence of crimes in the rural community, a public official from a state authority or local public authority is known, who, due to the lack of cooperation with the police employee, or ignoring it, the crime given is not properly recorded or investigated, which contributes to diminishing the public's confidence towards the state authorities.

In the Programme of Public Order and Security for 2022-2025, approved by Government Decision No 913/2022, the concept of community police activity was piloted with the support of partners and had a positive impact in the 5 piloting zones. Further development of the concept at national level, according to the same approach, is an opportunity for the widespread implementation of new methods and tools for the benefit of the population, which would also contribute to the prevention of rural crime.

However, against the background of an insufficient number of employees, a weakness, highlighted at the level of the public security precincts of police inspectorates, is inefficient planning of forces. The forces available in the subdivisions are not managed in a single dislocation system, and this makes the division of forces deficient. Lamentable is the fact that the managers of the territorial subdivisions of the police do not have sufficient will and capacity to unblock the situation, and the employees of the operational level are therefore overburdened [8], a situation which is necessary to be taken into account until some duties are given to the sector officer to carry out his/her activity both in the field of activity and through the inter-institutional collaboration process.

As the main law enforcement force, the police have a central position in preventing rural crime. With the responsibility of maintaining public order, investigating crimes and bringing perpetrators to justice, as part of this process, the police must maintain regular and

effective communication with other authorities and organisations to identify and address emerging issues. This may include sharing information on crime trends, working on developing crime prevention strategies and coordinating law enforcement efforts with other crime prevention initiatives.

We believe that the inter-institutional cooperation between the ministries of the Republic of Moldova is one of the factors that can contribute to the reduction of rural crime and its prevention.

The element of inter-institutional collaboration to prevent rural crime is also reflected in the 2021-2025 Crime Prevention Strategy developed by the Essex Police, UK, where at the very beginning of the strategy it is mentioned that it is part of a partnership approach to provide a full systemic response to the problems that cause the most damage to our communities. Thus, the police are committed to doing whatever is necessary to respond to the difficulties they face. Ensuring help for citizens, protecting their safety and catching those who break the law, is achieved through partnerships dedicated to reducing and preventing crime, representing the essence of the work [19].

As an example set out in the strategy developed by the Essex Police, which includes representatives of the Partnerships for Community Safety, Essex Police, Essex Firefighters and Rescue Service, health workers, partners in the field of criminal justice, probation, education and, in the case of the Republic of Moldova, we consider possible institutional cooperation between the police and the Ministry of Health, the National Administration of Penitentiaries, Probation Offices, Public Associations, NGOs.

Analysing the process of cooperation of the state authorities with the members of rural communities, we establish that, taking into account all the circumstances and particularities of activity, the police employee has the basic duties in preventing crime, being the representative of the state authority that must direct the cooperation between other state authorities with the rural community.

We believe that, in order to achieve a positive result in the activity process and to

achieve the objectives of preventing rural crime and maintaining a safe environment, contrary to some criminological conceptions, the police officer is to combine law enforcement and community rules, for which reason and it is necessary that he possess sufficient powers to coordinate and dispose of actions between other state authorities or public organisations.

Principles and approaches used in urban areas, which often rely on strict law enforcement in a context of weaker moral consensus, can have a negative impact in rural areas, where there is a more personal relationship between representatives of public authorities and citizens, and more emphasis is placed on moral consensus in problem solving and law enforcement.

It is therefore essential that police officers facing such situations are well trained and equipped, receive adequate training and training to understand the specificities of rural communities and effectively address their chal-

lenges and needs in the context of institutional collaboration and prevention of rural crime.

4. CONCLUSION.

Inter-institutional collaboration plays a crucial role in making rural crime prevention strategies more effective. Integrating efforts between police, government institutions, specialised public authorities, local authorities and non-governmental organisations is the foundation of a holistic and sustainable approach to combating rural crime. By sharing resources, exchanging information and coordinating actions, these entities can develop and implement preventive measures tailored to the specifics and needs of rural communities.

Thus, inter-institutional collaboration not only enhances the effectiveness of public security interventions, but also contributes to strengthening social cohesion and promoting a safe and prosperous environment for all inhabitants of rural communities.

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